

ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT CONCEPT AND DEVELOPMENT STAGES.

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about Electronic Government. In recent years, many developed countries of the world have been changing their traditional state structures to electronic government structures. In the same process, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been carrying out the necessary work using the experiences of the developed countries of the world. Of course, in this process, the government should have its own chosen direction, and Uzbekistan should have its own strategy. The main purpose of this article is to explain the concept of e-government, the stages of development of e-government in Uzbekistan and the ongoing work.

Key words: Electronic government, E-Government, electronic commerce, openness and transparency of state bodies; equal use of electronic government services by applicants; "single window", online store.

Electronic government is a system of organizational and legal measures and technical tools aimed at ensuring the provision of public services to individuals and legal entities, as well as interdepartmental electronic cooperation. There are several definitions of e-government. Broadly speaking, e-government can be defined as the use of ICT to improve the performance and performance of e-government functions and services.

In its own way, e-government can be understood as "a system of using digital technologies in order to increase the transparency, efficiency and quality of services provided by public authorities." Also, e-government is a more efficient operation of state bodies using ICT and providing high-quality services to citizens and business entities.

E-government terms are summarized by the following four main parts and described as follows [1].

1. Use of ICT (computer networks, Internet, fax and telephone).
2. Support of government activities (information provision, services, products, administrative management).
3. Development of government relations with citizens (creation of new communication channels, involvement of citizens in political or administrative processes through propaganda and campaigns)
4. Determining the value of participation of participants in the processes in accordance with the established strategies.

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Definitions of electronic government
United Nations
Electronic government is the use of the Internet to provide information and services to citizens by government agencies.
World Bank
Electronic government involves the improvement of relations between citizens, business entities and other state bodies using information technologies of state bodies. These technologies can serve various purposes: better delivery of public services to citizens, improvement of interaction with business and industry, expansion of citizen's rights and opportunities by obtaining necessary information, or implementation of more effective public administration.

Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development

The term e-government refers to the use of ICT by the government to fully perform a number of practical functions. In particular, the transformation of network capacity structures and government operations offered by the Internet and related technologies is understood.

The main tasks of e-government are:

- to ensure the effectiveness, speed, and transparency of the activities of state bodies, to strengthen their responsibility and executive discipline, to create additional mechanisms for ensuring the exchange of information with the population and business entities;
- to create opportunities for applicants to interact with state bodies throughout the country within the framework of electronic government;
- creation of databases of state bodies, the Unified interactive portal of state services and the unified register of electronic state services within the framework of assigned tasks;
- introduction of the "single window" principle in the public administration system due to the formation of electronic document circulation, mutual cooperation of state bodies and information exchange mechanisms between their databases in the implementation of mutual relations with the population and business entities;
- to encourage business entities to use electronic document circulation, including in the process of submitting statistical reports, customs clearance, licenses, permits, certificates, as well as information from state authorities
- to expand the use of electronic commerce, the Internet global information network and the use of systems for the sale and purchase of products by business entities, as well as the introduction of automated systems of accounting, control and payment for utility services;
- development of non-cash electronic payments, implementation of state procurement, remote access systems and other electronic forms of activity in the field of banking and finance[2].

The main principles of e-government are as follows:

- openness and transparency of the activities of state bodies;
- equal use of electronic government services by applicants;
- provision of electronic state services according to the "single window" principle;
- unification of documents of state bodies;
- use of unique identifiers of electronic government;
- regularly improving the procedure for providing electronic state services;
- ensuring information security.

In order to realize the possibilities of e-government, many countries are including it in their political plans for the development of e-government. The initial focus was on increasing the efficiency of government work through the use of ICT. However, as a result of limited government investment in e-government services, results shifted toward a citizen-centric approach in the mid-2000s. As a result of this approach, the delivery of government services has led to significant changes by prioritizing the suitability of the various needs of citizens to government services. Today, e-government is not only an important tool for the development and support of public sector tasks and processes, but also a key tool for transforming government and creating new approaches to service development and delivery.

In general, the increase in online services, the wider use of these services, in turn, indicates that the impact of the e-government system is great. Thus, e-government requires the presence of a critical mass of e-citizens and e-business participants to develop sustainable production, affecting government transparency and internal efficiency. It is necessary to increase the critical mass of users of e-government services, abandoning the traditional service delivery method and moving to the e-government service delivery method. and this process is not easy[3].

The implementation and use of the electronic government system will be successful only when there are requirements and support from the majority of the population. Part of the population's demands are fulfilled by the sufficient knowledge of the population about this system, its capabilities, and by providing public services quickly and well. Citizens and entrepreneurs should have interest or motivation in using e-government services, provide actual, easily accessible digital content services.

In addition, the state should ensure the protection of data and its confidentiality in order to increase the confidence of the community in electronic services.

To increase the level of support and requirements for the use of e-government services, the following actions should be carried out:

- development of a multi-channel single window common service delivery infrastructure, autonomous community service center and locations, including telecenters, call processing centers, web and mobile portals;
- Implementation of team trust measures for operations involving ICT and all interactions in the digital environment;
- material and moral incentives for producers of convenient content and services, including programs that meet the specified requirements, called "application termination";
- implementation of programs aimed at expanding and improving electronic services and their capabilities.

Regulatory and legal foundations of the development of the "Electronic Government" system Information and communication technologies are considered one of the main factors of development of social and economic spheres. In particular, the wide implementation of information and communication technologies in public administration is gaining importance in determining the future development of Uzbekistan[4].

Systematic reforms are being carried out in our country regarding the formation of the national information system, the expansion of the use of

modern information technologies and telecommunication tools in all spheres of economic and social activity, and the formation of electronic government. In order to strengthen the legal foundations of the formation of electronic government, "On guarantees and freedom of information", "On telecommunications", "On informationization", "On electronic digital signature" ", "On Electronic Document Circulation", "On Electronic Payments", "On Electronic Commerce", "On Openness of Activities of State Power and Management Bodies" Laws on" were adopted.

On July 1, 2013, more than 267 interactive public services, which ease the burden of many people, began to be provided electronically through the Unified Interactive State Services Portal. We can see the importance of these services from 564,000 requests to the portal by users over the past period.

The introduction of modern information and communication technologies in education, banking and finance, customs, tax and legal systems is highly effective today.

Legislation regulating the relations of e-government participants, the complete formation of centralized databases that serve to provide high-quality public services, the adequate implementation of modern information and communication technologies in the work of state bodies, and the provision of public services to citizens and entrepreneurs. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Government" was adopted to eliminate the problems in the full use of the "single window" principle.

The main purpose of this Law is to protect the interests of the population and entrepreneurs in the provision of public services, to create a wide range of conveniences for them, to save their time, to reduce wasteful distractions and excessive spending, and to increase the efficiency of the activities of state bodies. The law regulates the interaction of state bodies with legal entities and individuals in the provision of electronic state services, including in the framework of interdepartmental electronic cooperation[5].

The law consists of 5 chapters and 34 articles. The law defines its goals and tasks, basic concepts, basic principles of e-government, organization of its work, standards for the provision of e-state services. Also, the Law regulates the relations of electronic government infrastructure, public administration in this area, and mutual cooperation of state bodies within the framework of electronic government.

Concepts such as e-government, public service, interdepartmental electronic cooperation, e-state service, regulation of e-state service, and unique identifiers of e-government are being included in the legislation for the first time and are being defined accordingly. The basic principles of the electronic government system are consolidated in the law. Among these are principles such as openness and transparency of the activities of state bodies, equal use of electronic state services by applicants, provision of electronic state services according to the "single window" principle, and ensuring information security.

The law defines the norms of state regulation of the field of electronic government. According to it, the Cabinet of Ministers is entrusted with the tasks of ensuring the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of electronic government, approving and monitoring the implementation of state programs in this field. The Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development as an authorized body in the field of e-government implements the unified state policy in the field of e-government in accordance with the principles of e-government. Coordinates the activities of state bodies in the field of electronic government. State bodies participate in the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of electronic government, ensure the introduction, development and integration of information resources and systems, as well as electronic state services.

In accordance with the law, users can receive information about the activities of state bodies or be provided with interactive state services. The

law specifies the requirements for these types of electronic state services, the procedure for sending requests for their use, and the rights of users.

According to the law, the state information service is aimed at satisfying the information needs of the population, in which state bodies deliver information about their activities to the general public.

The introduction of interactive public service serves to increase the quality of bilateral cooperation between the population and state bodies[6].

At the same time, the Law establishes the procedure for assessing the quality of electronic state services and the obligation of state bodies to take measures to improve the quality of electronic state services, taking into account the results of the assessment. This corresponds to the principle of regular improvement of the procedure for providing public services.

Following the implementation of the law, the following results will be achieved:

First, the legal basis for the introduction and development of the "Electronic Government" system will be created in our country, and the foundation will be created for the formation, full operation and systematic development of this system;

Secondly, the further deepening of democratic reforms in our country and the further deepening of democratic market reforms defined in the concept of civil society development will be the basis for ensuring the implementation of tasks such as prohibiting the introduction of new types of excessive permits and permit procedures, guaranteeing freedom of business activity;

Thirdly, the effectiveness of the activities of state authorities and management bodies, including management and administrative productivity, will increase, and their accountability and openness to the society will be ensured. In the end, people's confidence in government bodies will increase.

Fourthly, the quality of public services and the convenience of their use will increase for the population and business entities. Consequently,

innovative ideas are consistently introduced into the activities of state bodies, the business sector, document circulation mechanisms are improved, and interactive services are provided that allow citizens to apply electronically from their homes or offices, receive certificates and other documents, or organize business activities. ensures the sale.

The entry into force of the Law "On Electronic Government" together with the above-mentioned results will help to attract foreign investors by further deepening democratic reforms, improving the business environment, increasing people's well-being and development of the country. serves to ensure the rate of economic growth and is important for the socio-economic development of the regions.

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